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Email:dear246.dn@gmail.com**©2023. Gaybullayev Sarvar.****QISHLOQ XO'JALIGINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH SHAROITIDA
AGRAR IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH****DEVELOPMENT OF AGRARIAN ECONOMY IN THE
CONDITIONS OF DIGITIZATION OF AGRICULTURE****РАЗВИТИЕ АГРАРНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В УСЛОВИЯХ
ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ СЕЛЬСКОГО ХОЗЯЙСТВА****ANNOTATSIYA**

Ushbu maqolada respublikamizda qishloq xo'jaligini rivojlantirish uchun raqamlashtirish asosida iqtisodiy samaradorlikka erishish bo'yicha ilmiy-nazariy fikr-mulohazalar keltirilgan.

ANNOTATION

In this article, the scientific-theoretical opinion-comments on achieving economic efficiency on the basis of digitization for the development of the agricultural sector in our republic are presented.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье представлены научно-теоретические мнения-комментарии по достижению экономической эффективности на основе цифровизации для развития аграрного сектора нашей республики.

KALIT SO'ZLAR

agroiqtisodiyot, raqamlashtirish siyosati islohotlari, iqtisodiy qarorlar, iqtisodiyot elementlari, texnologiya, tranzaksiya xarajatlari

KEYWORDS

agro economy, digitization policy reforms, economic decisions, elements of economy, technology, transaction costs

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

агроэкономика, реформы политики цифровизации, экономические решения, элементы экономики, технологии, транзакционные издержки

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INTRODUCTION

The effectiveness of the digitization of the agricultural industry can be increased by creating an electronic platform for the sale of goods of the agro-industrial complex, where transactions are concluded not only with intermediaries, but also with end buyers. Elements of digital economy can be used for land and crop monitoring, optimization of calculations between producer and buyer, rationalization of investment and credit system, social insurance.

Digitization ensures active use of marketing methods, resistance to monopoly, creation of conditions for electronic interaction between all participants of the economy.

MAIN PART

Digitization of agriculture, that is, optimization of the agrarian sector with the help of modern technologies and digital solutions, is very important for developing countries like Uzbekistan. Development of agrarian economy through digitization can be done in the following ways:

Data Analysis and Decision Making: With the help of digital technologies, farmers can more accurately analyze various data like weather, soil condition, crop condition and take decisions accordingly. This helps to increase productivity.

Modern Digital Tools: With the help of satellite images, drones, sensors and other modern technologies, it is possible to monitor the condition of the crops and carry out the necessary maintenance. For example, early detection of diseases or pests and taking effective measures against them.

Smart Irrigation Systems: In water-scarce areas, water can be used more efficiently through smart water distribution systems. This improves water resource management and helps conserve water.

E-Marketplaces: Using digital technologies to expand the market for products and allow farmers to sell their products directly to consumers or wholesalers.

Education and Upskilling: Through digital technologies, farmers can be informed and

upskilled about modern agricultural methods, new technologies.

Lending and Financial Assistance: Through digital banking services and lending systems, farmers can be helped to get the necessary funds to grow their businesses.

Public Policy and Support: It is very important for the government to apply incentives such as investments, subsidies, and tax breaks to the digital agriculture sector.

Actions in these directions will have a positive effect not only on increasing the efficiency of agriculture, but also on economic growth, ensuring employment of the population, and environmental protection.

Digitization of agriculture, that is, optimization of the agrarian sector with the help of modern information and communication technologies, plays an important role in the development of the agrarian economy. Through digitization, it is possible to increase the efficiency of farming, rational use of resources, reduce environmental problems and improve the quality of agricultural products. Below are the main points to focus on in this process:

Implementation of Modern Information Systems: With the help of such systems, it is possible to monitor crop areas, predict productivity, and quickly identify pests and diseases.

Artificial Intelligence and Data Analysis: By collecting and analyzing data, agricultural producers can optimize plant and animal growth conditions, as well as manage resources (water, fertilizer, energy) can be effectively managed.

Automated Control Systems: These systems enable precise dosing of water and fertilizers by automating, for example, water supply and fertilization systems, which helps save resources.

Drones and Remotely Controlled Technologies: Using drones, it is possible to monitor agricultural fields, assess the condition of plants and take quick action when necessary.

Digital traceability of agricultural products: This approach allows for traceability of product

origin and quality, which increases consumer confidence and makes products more competitive.

Education and Skill Development: It is very important to train farmers in new technologies and methods and improve their skills. For this, it is necessary to organize distance learning platforms and practical seminars.

Environmental Resilience: Digitization can make agriculture more resilient to natural disasters, such as choosing and planting crops that adapt to climate change.

Financial and Insurance Technologies: Digitization will make lending and insurance services more efficient and easier, thereby ensuring financial security for farmers.

By implementing these directions, it is possible to develop agriculture and increase its competitiveness. However, this process requires a comprehensive approach and must be flexible to local conditions.

Directed digitization. To develop the segment of digital technologies, it is necessary to prepare an advanced information and communication infrastructure. To solve the problems facing the digital economy, we need relevant knowledge bases, information resources and interactive teams, a wide network of integrated business platforms, digital environment and personnel who can work in new conditions. Such a comprehensive approach makes it possible to create a digital ecosystem in which each participant plays a dual role - a client and a data server. This creates the basis for topic-oriented clusters in which agrarian digital ecosystems operate.

The use of digital technologies has a positive effect on the growth rates of productivity and profitability in the agro-industrial complex. A clear example of this is Israel, where only 20% of the land resources are suitable for agricultural activities, and at the same time, the food supply of the population is 95%. In this case, the lack of favorable natural and climatic conditions is compensated by the possibilities of innovative technologies. Another example of the effectiveness of introducing digital technologies into the agro-industrial complex is the creation of "smart" farms.

This technology allows to increase milk production by 30-40% on average, the use of modern methods of transport management allows to reduce fuel costs by 20%.

The development of an agrarian economy in the context of the digitization of agriculture is a multifaceted process involving the integration of advanced digital technologies into traditional agricultural practices. This transformation aims to enhance efficiency, productivity, sustainability, and profitability in the agricultural sector. Here are some key aspects of this development:

1. Precision Agriculture.

GPS Technology: Enables precise planting, fertilizing, and harvesting, reducing waste and increasing crop yields.

Sensors and IoT: Sensors in the field monitor conditions like soil moisture, nutrient levels, and weather, allowing for more informed decision-making.

2. Data Analytics and AI

Predictive Analytics: Utilize data to forecast weather patterns, pest infestations, and crop yields, aiding in preemptive decision-making.

Machine Learning: Helps in identifying disease patterns, improving crop selection, and optimizing resource use.

3. Automation and Robotics

Drones: Used for crop monitoring, spraying, and mapping fields.

Autonomous Tractors and Harvesters: Reduce the need for manual labor and increase the precision of field operations.

4. Supply Chain Management

Blockchain: Enhances traceability and transparency in the supply chain, from farm to table.

Smart Logistics: Optimizes distribution routes and storage conditions, reducing waste and improving product quality.

5. Sustainable Practices

Resource Management: More efficient use of water, fertilizers, and pesticides, reducing environmental impact.

Renewable Energy: Integration of solar, wind, or bioenergy sources to power agricultural operations.

6. Farmer Support and Education

Digital Platforms: Provide farmers with access to information, market trends, and online training resources.

Government Policies and Subsidies: Support the adoption of digital technologies in agriculture.

7. Challenges and Considerations

Digital Divide: Ensuring equitable access to technology for all farmers, including those in remote or underprivileged areas.

Cybersecurity: Protecting the vast amounts of data generated from cyber threats.

Ethical and Legal Issues: Addressing concerns related to data ownership and privacy.

8. Economic Impact

Increased Productivity: Higher yields and reduced waste contribute to economic growth.

Job Creation: New technologies create opportunities in tech support, data analysis, and drone operation.

Market Competitiveness: Enhanced quality and efficiency can improve market positioning for farmers and nations.

9. Global Perspective

Adaptation to Different Regions: Customizing digital solutions to suit local climates, cultures, and farming practices.

International Collaboration: Sharing knowledge and technology across borders to advance global food security.

10. Future Prospects

Integration of Advanced Technologies: Potential use of nanotechnology, advanced biotechnology, and more sophisticated AI systems.

Smart Rural Communities: Developing wider digital ecosystems that connect agriculture with other sectors like healthcare, education, and e-commerce.

CONCLUSION

The digitization of agriculture offers a transformative path for the agrarian economy, making it more efficient, sustainable, and

profitable. However, it's crucial to address the associated challenges and ensure that the benefits are widely and equitably distributed. The future of agrarian economies in the digital era looks promising, with endless possibilities for innovation and improvement.

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